

Effects of BaSO₄ nano-particles on the enhancement of the optical performance of white LEDs

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ABSTRACT

The usage of BaSO₄ nanoparticles on WLEDs luminous flux and color uniformity improvements have been analyzed and demonstrated in this manuscript. The mixture of BaSO₄ and silicone placed on the yellow phosphor layer benefits the internal light scattering and thus enhances the angular correlated color temperature (CCT) homogeneity. Specifically, the blue-light intensity at large angles tend to increase and results in light intensity discrepancy, which can be corrected with added BaSO₄. In addition to this, the BaSO₄-silicone composite modifies the refractive index of the air-phosphor layer interface to an appropriate value, and thus, the luminous efficiency increases. The results show that the CCT deviations is reduced by 580 K, from 1000 K to 420 K, within the angle range from -70° to +70° with BaSO₄ in the phosphor structure. The increase in luminous flux is also recorded by 2.25%, in comparison with that of the non-BaSO₄ traditional structure, at the 120-mA driving current. Hence, integrating BaSO₄ nanoparticles into the remote phosphor structure can contribute to the enhancement of both lumen output and CCT uniformity.

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1. INTRODUCTION

High-power white light-emitting diodes (WLEDs) have been proposed as a potential lighting source for solid-state lighting (SSL) devices, which could replace the traditional one [1, 2]. Several techniques to manufacture WLEDs have been applied, yet the most popular one is dispersing yellow Y₃Al₅O₁₂ (YAG) phosphor on the blue LED chip. The LEDs fabricated by this method is called phosphor-converted white light-emitting diodes (pc-LEDs) [3-5]. The pc-LEDs can offer a high lighting efficiency and also a cost-saving production process, but they have not yielded good color uniformity and high light extraction at the air-phosphor layer interface. Meanwhile, enhancing the lumen efficiency of WLEDs by elevating the light extraction has been focused and researched extensively in recent studies [6-8]. Thus, researchers have come up with many packaging structures, for instances, using a hemi-spherically shaped encapsulation [9] and the ELiXIR pc-LEDs structure with internal reflection, to accomplish high light extraction [10]. However, the light loss still occurs in these structures, which reduce the overall efficiency of WLEDs [11, 12]. In particular, a considerable portion of yellow rays emitted from the yellow phosphor layer are scattered back to the LED chip

and finally being absorbed. Researchers figured out that to avoid the backscattering effect, the solution is to address the re-absorption issue by providing a sufficient distance between the LED chip and the phosphor layer. Therefore, innovative structures were introduced to achieve this purpose, including the ring-remote structure and scattered photon extraction (SPE) [13-15].

According to the findings from previous articles, the remote phosphor structure is proved to have superior lumen efficacy to traditional dispersing design. However, throughout the duration of fabricating the remote phosphor structure, there is a problem related to the surface of the concave encapsulant, which is the phosphor thickness inhomogeneity [16-18]. Additionally, the angular-dependent blue light paths of this packaging design usually cause a non-uniform excitation, leading to the yellow ring phenomenon. Thus, we proposed to apply BaSO₄ nanoparticles to the remote packaging design of WLEDs as a solution for this issue. The purpose of using BaSO₄ material is to take advantage of its superior scattering ability to enhance the blue light intensity at large angles, from which the angular color correlated temperature (CCT) homogeneity is elevated [19-22]. In addition to this, the refractive index at the interface of the air and phosphor film is adjusted with the addition of BaSO₄, and thus, the luminous efficiency is also enhanced.

2. EXPERIMENT

The schematic diagrams of WLEDs are illustrated in Figure 1. The process of producing conventional remote phosphor structure is comprised of 3 main steps. Firstly, the blue LED chips are attached to the lead frame. Secondly, the transparent silicone glue is dispensed into the lead frame and cured at the temperature of 150 °C within an hour. Thirdly, a slurry of phosphor suspension is created by the blending the phosphor powers, silicone binding agent, and alkyl-based solvent together. In addition, according to previous studied, the uniformity of the phosphor slurry can be improved by using the pulse spray coating method with an interval control. Afterwards, this slurry is placed onto the silicone surface to complete the remote structure which is presented in Figure 1 (a). The blue LED chips used in the experimented model are the 24-mil-square ones whose emission wavelengths peak at 450 nm. Additionally, each bare LED chip has 95 mW radiant flux at 120 mA driving current. The yellow phosphor Y₃Al₅O₁₂ (YAG) particle has a size of 12 μm.

The process of fabricating remote phosphor structure with BaSO₄ is similar to the traditional one, but BaSO₄ is used instead of the yellow phosphor to combine with the other two materials. The simulated of BaSO₄ remote phosphor packaging is shown in Figure 1 (b). Moreover, the BaSO₄ is added with the concentration of 5%. The input parameters of the LED chips in this structure is the same as those in the conventional one. Through the cross-sectional scanning electron microscopic (SEM) image, we can know that the particle size of BaSO₄ in the silicone encapsulant is approximately 300 nm. Besides, the energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) is utilized to analyze the components of the encapsulant containing BaSO₄ and silicone.

Figure 1. (a) Photograph of WLEDs sample, (b) The simulated WLEDs model

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The general definition of the angular-dependent CCT homogeneity can be demonstrated as the following equation [23-25]:

$$\text{Angular-dependent CCT uniformity} = \text{Max CCT} - \text{Min CCT}$$

Figure 2 shows the changes of CCT deviations in connection with different particles weight of BaSO₄. As can be seen, the deviation of CCT reaches its lowest level when the weight of BaSO₄ is 10 mg cm⁻². The results

present that this is the optimal weight for BaSO₄ to be applied as the CCT uniformity can be improved by 58%, or in other words, the CCT deviations reduce from 1000 K to 420 K in the angles from -70° to 70°, in comparison with that of the traditional structure. In the traditional packaging structure, the extraction of blue lights at large angles is inferior as they are trapped and reflected within the phosphor layer, and this phenomenon results in the inhomogeneous color mixing of blue and yellow rays. On the other hand, when added BaSO₄ the scattering events are improved, leading to a more uniform distribution of the blue and yellow lights. When the weight of BaSO₄ is more than 10 mg cm⁻², the CCT deviations are also affected. However, the structure with >10 mg cm⁻² still performs better than the conventional design.

In addition, the experiment outcomes indicate that the 10 mg cm⁻² BaSO₄ yields better luminous efficiency, as presented in Figure 3. At the driving current of 120 mA, the BaSO₄ structure can achieve 2.25% enhancement in luminous efficiency. Furthermore, the refractive index variation at the air-encapsulant interface is degraded, which probably increases the light extraction efficiency. As the BaSO₄-silicone film has the refractive index of 1.5, and the phosphor-silicone's is 1.8, the BaSO₄ will result in a sufficient gradient between air and the encapsulant layer.

Figure 2. CCT deviations of BaSO₄ particles with different diameters

Figure 3. Luminous fluxes of BaSO₄ particles with different diameters

To investigate more about BaSO₄ scattering ability in the visible range, the haze intensity is calculated by the two parameters: the total transmittance and the diffractive transmittance (non-specular transmittance), which can be expressed as [26]:

$$\text{Haze intensity} = T_{\text{diffraction}}/T_{\text{total}} \times 100\%$$

The diffractive and total transmittances are presented by $T_{\text{diffraction}}$ and T_{total} , respectively. Additionally, it is noted that the diffractive transmittance does not include the zero-order diffraction. The computed results demonstrated that the haze intensity of the non-BaSO₄ silicone layer stays at a low level which is around 0%. However, this parameter shows an upward trend when BaSO₄ appears in the silicone film, and tends to develop along with the increase in BaSO₄ particle weight. Moreover, the scattering is likely to be stronger as the haze

intensity is higher. Besides, the better the scattering ability is, the more uniform the angular CCT becomes. Thus, BaSO₄ is a solution for the inhomogeneous CCT problem.

The changes of blue and yellow light scattering intensities in the normal direction with various BaSO₄ diameters are analyzed by using the full-field finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) simulation for the illustration of the impacts of BaSO₄ particle sizes on angular-dependent CCT and lumen efficacy. Given that BaSO₄-silicon layer's refractive index is 1.5, and BaSO₄ concentration is 5%, 400 nm turns out to be the most effective diameter of BaSO₄ as it can accomplish higher angular-dependent scattering intensity in the blue and yellow light (450 nm and 560 nm, respectively), compared to results of the other sizes. Though the color uniformity is obviously enhanced with the improvement in the light scattering, the blue and yellow light transmittance show some disadvantages. One of them is the increased absorption as the thickness of the BaSO₄-silicon layer grows, which will decrease the luminous performance. With BaSO₄ diameter at 300 nm, the absorbed light can make up 5-15% of the total amount, and this number tends to increase if the size of BaSO₄ becomes larger. Thus, the light absorption must be considered together with the light scattering when choosing the appropriate diameter for BaSO₄ nanoparticle so that WLED devices can achieve better CCT uniformity and light output power.

The influence that BaSO₄ has on the emission of the structure is investigated by the measurements of blue and yellow light angular-dependent relative intensity. It is reported that in BaSO₄ remote structure, the variety of blue light angles increases while the normal-direction blue light decreases in comparison to the conventional one. This implies the strong impacts of BaSO₄ scattering property on the light path of the blue photons that cause the increase of CCT deviation. Meanwhile, the light distribution of yellow rays in BaSO₄ remote phosphor structure is nearly the same as that in the conventional package. This phenomenon can be explained by the wavelength-dependent haze ratio of 10 mg cm⁻² BaSO₄ layer: its haze for yellow light with wavelength at about 600 nm is 30%, while for the ~ 450 nm blue rays is 35%. The higher haze percent results in the strong light scattered. Therefore, it can be said that the yellow-light scattering events are less than the blue-light ones, contributing to the lower CCT deviation as the blue and yellow lights are mixed more uniformly. Additionally, the haze measurement exhibits that the diffused component of 600 nm yellow light is half that of the 450 nm blue ray. Concluded from these findings, the CCT deviation has a close connection with the blue-light angle variations. Moreover, the blue-light relative intensity that is dependent on BaSO₄ weight was studied at the angle of 70°. The results reveal that 10 mg cm⁻² BaSO₄ is the most advantageous condition for the enhancement of WLEDs CCT uniformity as it exhibits the highest blue-light intensity at large angles.

4. CONCLUSION

The enhancement in CCT homogeneity and light output with the addition of BaSO₄ in the silicone layer is reported in this article. In particular, BaSO₄-silicone layer can get 58% improvement of CCT uniformity in comparison with the conventional design. Moreover, the presence of BaSO₄ helps to increase the lumen output by 2.25% at the driving current of 120 mA. The scattering effect of BaSO₄ is also analyzed through the haze intensity measurement. The outcomes reveal that the remote structure with 10 mg cm⁻² BaSO₄ can achieve the lowest angular CCT deviation level. In addition to this, the yellow ring phenomenon is likely eliminated without sacrificing the lighting output. Hence, manufacturers can use 10 mg cm⁻² BaSO₄ in the remote phosphor structure to accomplish high-quality WLED generation.

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